

CORRECTION

[View Article Online](#)
[View Journal](#) | [View Issue](#)

Correction: High-capacitance polyurethane ionogels for low-voltage operated organic transistors and pressure sensors

Cite this: *J. Mater. Chem. C*, 2021, 9, 1108

Grace Dansoa Tabi,^{ad} Joo Sung Kim,^b Benjamin Nketia-Yawson,^a Do Hwan Kim^{*be} and Yong-Young Noh^{*c}

DOI: 10.1039/d1tc90006d

Correction for 'High-capacitance polyurethane ionogels for low-voltage operated organic transistors and pressure sensors' by Grace Dansoa Tabi et al., *J. Mater. Chem. C*, 2020, **8**, 17107–17113, DOI: 10.1039/D0TC02364G.

rsc.li/materials-c

The authors regret an error in the published article where the name of the last author, Yong-Young Noh, was incorrectly shown as Young-Yong Noh. The corrected list of author names for this article is as shown here.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

^a Department of Energy and Materials Engineering, Dongguk University, 30 Pildong-ro 1-Gil, Jung-gu, Seoul 04620, Republic of Korea

^b Department of Chemical Engineering, Hanyang University, Seoul 04763, Republic of Korea. E-mail: dhkim76@hanyang.ac.kr, dohwan76.kim@gmail.com

^c Department of Chemical Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology (POSTECH), Pohang, 37673, Republic of Korea. E-mail: yynoh@postech.ac.kr

^d Research School of Electrical, Energy and Materials Engineering, The Australian National University, Canberra 2601, Australia

^e Institute of Nano Science and Technology, Hanyang University, Seoul 04763, Republic of Korea

